

ХИВА ХОНЛИГИДА МЕТАЛЛСОЗЛИК ИХТИСОСЛАШУВИ ВА ХУНАРМАНДЧИЛИК УЮШМАЛАРИНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ

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Аннотация

Мазкур мақолада XV–XX асрлар давомида Хива хонлиги ҳудудида металлсозлик соҳаларидаги ихтисослашув жараёнлари ва хунармандчилик тизимининг шаклланиши илмий манбалар асосида таҳлил қилинади. Тадқиқотда шаҳар ва қишлоқ муҳитида металлга ишлов берувчи касбларнинг тармоқланиши, меҳнат тақсимоти, ҳудудий ихтисослашув ва ташқи иқтисодий омилларнинг таъсири ёритиб берилади. Шунингдек, XIX аср охири - XX аср бошларида Чор Россияси саноат маҳсулотларининг маҳаллий хунармандчиликка кўрсатган таъсири ҳам таҳлил қилинади.

Калит сўзлар

Металлсозлик, ихтисослашув, хунармандчилик, Хива хонлиги, меҳнат тақсимоти, темирчилик, қишлоқ хунармандчилиги

ПРОЦЕССЫ СПЕЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ В МЕТАЛЛУРГИЧЕСКОМ РЕМЕСЛЕ И РЕМЕСЛЕННЫЕ ОБЪЕДИНЕНИЯ В ХИВИНСКОМ ХАНСТВЕ

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Аннотация

В статье анализируются процессы специализации в металлургическом ремесле и формирование ремесленной структуры на территории Хивинского ханства в XV–XX веках. На основе письменных источников и этнографических материалов рассматриваются профессиональное разделение труда, городская и сельская металлургия, территориальная специализация и влияние внешнеэкономических факторов. Особое внимание уделяется упадку традиционных ремёсел в конце XIX – начале XX веков в связи с проникновением промышленной продукции Российской империи.

Ключевые слова

Металлургическое ремесло, специализация, Хивинское ханство, ремесленники, разделение труда, кузнечество.

PROCESSES OF SPECIALIZATION IN METALWORKING AND CRAFT ORGANIZATION IN THE KHIVA KHANATE

Abstract

This article examines the processes of specialization in metalworking crafts and the development of craft organization in the territory of the Khiva Khanate from the fifteenth to the early twentieth centuries. Based on historical, written, and ethnographic sources, the study analyzes internal labor division, professional differentiation, urban and rural metalworking practices, and regional specialization. Particular attention is paid to the decline of traditional crafts in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries as a result of the influx of industrial metal products from the Russian Empire.

Keywords

Metalworking, specialization, craftsmanship, Khiva Khanate, division of labor, blacksmithing

Introduction

Metalworking was one of the most important branches of traditional craftsmanship in Central Asia and played a decisive role in shaping the economic structure of medieval cities and rural settlements. In the territory of the Khiva Khanate, metal crafts not only ensured the production of agricultural tools, household items, and weapons but also reflected broader socio-economic transformations, including labor division, professional specialization, and regional differentiation. The gradual emergence of specialized crafts and organized workshops illustrates the transition from household-based production to more complex forms of artisanal manufacture.

This article aims to analyze the processes of specialization in metalworking crafts and the formation of craft organization in the Khiva Khanate from the fifteenth to the early twentieth centuries, using written historical sources, craft manuals, archival documents, and ethnographic materials.

By the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries, major urban centers such as Bukhara and Samarkand had already developed a well-defined internal division of labor within metalworking crafts. Numerous specialized professions emerged, including cast-iron workers, tool makers, belt producers, weapon smiths, sickle makers, nail makers, needle makers, knife makers, farriers, locksmiths, bronze casters, copper smiths, and jewelers [1]. These cities served as advanced models of craft specialization within the broader Central Asian region.

In contrast, the Khorezm region experienced a slower and less intensive process of specialization during the sixteenth to eighteenth centuries. Political instability and economic fluctuations limited the expansion of highly differentiated craft sectors. Nevertheless, even under these conditions, certain specialized professions developed and maintained their significance. One such profession was seal engraving (muhrkanlik), which involved producing seals from gold, silver, copper, and bronze.

Abulg'azi Bahadur Khan's seventeenth-century historical work provides important evidence for the existence of professional seal engravers. He records instances in which seal engravers were brought from local markets to produce personalized seals for rulers and noble

figures [2][3]. The fact that seal engravers could be readily found in bazaars indicates that this craft had already achieved the status of an independent and specialized profession by the seventeenth century.

Craft manuals, known as “*risola*”s, represent an essential source for understanding professional organization and ethical norms among artisans. According to the “*risola*”, craftsmanship consisted of forty-one distinct professions, highlighting the early recognition of professional diversity within artisanal production. The emergence of such manuals is closely associated with the spread of Islam, which influenced the moral, social, and professional frameworks of craft communities.

A mid-nineteenth-century blacksmithing *risola* preserved in a private archive from the Khonka district of Khorezm offers particularly valuable insights. It lists several specialized metalworking professions, including needle making, nail making, hoe making, knife making, jewelry making, and copper working, while noting the existence of many additional crafts [4]. This document confirms that by the nineteenth century, metalworking specialization in Khorezm had become more pronounced and systematized.

Socio-economic development in Khorezm during the nineteenth century significantly strengthened specialization within metalworking crafts. Although blacksmiths were collectively referred to as *damirchi*, they were internally differentiated according to the types of products they manufactured. These included knife makers, producers of agricultural tools such as axes, sickles, shovels, and hoes, nail makers, needle makers, locksmiths, and farriers.

Knife making represented one of the oldest specialized crafts in the region, dating back to the eleventh and twelfth centuries. The advanced development of this craft is reflected in the widespread occurrence of the toponym “Pichoqchi” in various locations. Archival documents from 1864–1865 confirm the existence of a district named “Pichoqchi” in the Hazorasp beklik [5]. Additional records indicate that a settlement bearing the same name existed in the Hazorasp region during the 1830s, further demonstrating the long-standing specialization of knife production.

According to S. Turayeva’s monographic research, metalworking crafts occupied a central place in the economic life of the khanate and were divided into numerous specialized professions. These included metal engravers decorating copper vessels, copper smiths producing household utensils, gun makers, nail makers, seal engravers, brazier makers, wire inlay craftsmen, blacksmiths producing tools and household items, jewelers, plowshare makers, coin minters, farriers, bronze casters, spoon makers, sheath makers, locksmiths, and cauldron makers [6].

By the nineteenth century, this diversity reflected a high level of professional differentiation, indicating the maturation of artisanal production systems within the Khiva Khanate. Certain districts and cities became known for producing specific types of metal goods, further reinforcing regional specialization [7].

Urban metalworking workshops increasingly specialized in producing specific categories of goods. In Khiva, workshops focused on knife making and locksmithing, while Khonka specialized in sickle production. Tashhovuz became known for producing horseshoes, shovels, axes, and nails, whereas Khiva and Khojayli specialized in manufacturing equestrian equipment such as stirrups, bridles, and horseshoes. Blacksmith shops were typically located near city fortresses and marketplaces, facilitating access to raw materials and consumers.

Metal products were generally divided into three main categories: agricultural tools (hoes, shovels, sickles), carpentry tools (axes, saws, adzes), and household items (knives, scissors, shears, nails). The specialization of metalworking crafts was closely linked to the trade and economic potential of urban centers.

Metalworking was not confined to urban environments. Throughout all medieval periods, blacksmithing was widespread in rural settlements, where it was closely integrated with household-based production. Rural blacksmiths often combined farming with seasonal metalworking activities, producing tools primarily for local consumption. Payment was typically made in kind, such as grain or livestock, rather than in cash [9].

In larger villages, metal products were occasionally produced for local markets, especially during the later medieval period. Orders for blacksmiths were most frequent during autumn and winter, after the harvest season, and remuneration was commonly determined by village elders [10]. Unlike urban artisans, rural craftsmen did not form formal craft guilds or associations.

By the early twentieth century, Khiva housed not only individual blacksmith workshops but also larger establishments employing more than ten workers, each specializing in the production of a single type of item. The internal division of labor within these workshops resembled early manufacturing or proto-industrial forms of production [11]. This indicates that certain sectors of metalworking had begun transitioning toward more complex production systems.

However, following the conquest of the Khiva Khanate by the Russian Empire, traditional metalworking crafts experienced a sharp decline. Industrial metal products manufactured in Russian factories flooded local markets, undermining the competitiveness of local artisans. As a result, many specialized crafts disappeared by the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

Ethnographic research by I. Jabbarov confirms that by the early twentieth century, only a limited number of metalworking crafts remained in Khorezm's cities, including cast iron production, blacksmithing, copper working, jewelry making, locksmithing, knife making, and metal fitting [8].

The evolution of metalworking crafts in the Khiva Khanate demonstrates a complex process of specialization shaped by economic conditions, urban development, and external influences. From early professional differentiation to proto-manufacturing forms, metalworking reflected broader transformations within the region's economic history. Despite its eventual decline under colonial economic pressures, traditional metalworking remains a vital component of Khorezm's cultural and historical heritage.

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